

EFFECTIVE TRAINING AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TOWARDS SMALL ENTREPRENEUR DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Adequate training opportunities that can create effective small entrepreneurs in Bangladesh are a considerable area for investigation. This study aims to examine the necessity of training in the development of entrepreneurship in Bangladesh. A sample of 401 respondents has been selected conveniently from all over Bangladesh. SPSS has been used to input data and STTA has been used to analyze collected data for descriptive statistics, Proportion tests, chi-square tests, correlation analysis, ordinal logistic regression analysis, testing hypotheses, and other general analyses. After analyzing the correlation among the factors of training it is found that there is a positive relationship between entrepreneurship training and all several indicators to measure the effectiveness of training on small entrepreneurship. This research recommends that all training organizations ensure adequate training opportunities for the development of small entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Training; Opportunities; Effective training; Small Entrepreneur.

INTRODUCTION

An entrepreneur is creative. They are doing new things or something in new ways, such as introducing new technology in production or products with which consumers are not familiar or new markets that are now unfamiliar & unexplored. Henry et al. (2003) reveal that entrepreneurship is fundamental to participating in the present community due to its substantial international and national level ramifications. According to Donald & Richard (1995), the entrepreneur is the catalyst for economic change, which uses purposeful searching, careful planning, and sound judgment in carrying out the entrepreneurial process and working creatively to establish new resources or endow old ones with new capacity to create wealth. Hisrich and o'Kinneide (1985) indicate that entrepreneurship donates to the creation of innovative ideas, development of modernization, handpicked, and economic expansion.

It is also recognized that training policies have positive effects on large firms as well as small firms. Entrepreneurial competences and competencies can be approved and encouraged through training. Formal informal and vocational training can help increase entrepreneurship, improvement, and sustainable economy. CEDEFOP (2011), entrepreneurship training is pertinent in professional training as working for oneself is a practical opportunity for various vocational training and employment student (VET) students, who end up establishing their organization. The practical and technical skills obtained in technical training from the foundation for starting a fresh business, but technical skills only cannot facilitate an organization's carry-on business and make it successful. European Business Forum on Technical Training (2012) highlights that entrepreneurial mental state; expertise and ability are also needed to take full advantage

of the advantage of specialized skills and expertise for organizational achievement, expansion, achievement, and invention.

Entrepreneurship training means to learn knowledge and skills that a person needs to know before embarking on a new business. Training and motivation workshops and seminars are helpful for young people to be an entrepreneur in society and their hidden competencies come out through the motivation programs. Entrepreneurship training has been tinted as an entry requisite to the enlargement and expansion of the small business sector in a lot of countries of the earth. It has been accepted as a significant instrument for altering the behavior and moving of skills of people with entrepreneurial character.

According to Azim M. T. (2013), in his research stated that “Entrepreneurship education and training (EET) has acknowledged vast concentration from the academicians, researchers, and policy creators in current years in Bangladesh. He also mentioned that those who have joined training are more successful than the entrepreneurs who have not joined training”. Although Peterman and Kennedy (2003), the suspected reimbursement of entrepreneurship training has been famous by trainees and researchers, there has been a small exact study on its sound effects. Glaub & Frese (2011) stated that entrepreneurship training programs have had constructive special effects on an emotional element, enterprise management skills, and element success. In addition, training on emotional elements has a positive contact on organization expansion.

Peterman and Kennedy (2003); and Fayolle et al. (2006), in fact, education and entrepreneurship training position high on policy agendas in Europe and the US, but a few examine workers are accessible to find its effects and their impact. Many studies find an optimistic impact of entrepreneurship training and education programs on entrepreneurship development.

According to Sylvia Gavigan, Thomas M. Cooney, and Klavs Ciprikis (2023), an entrepreneurship training expansion of 25 entrepreneurial knowledge and again education training opportunities can expand the community status of countryside women functioning in agriculture. Again, this research can update managers, economists, and the government on the settlement of suitable education and training programs to progress the family values, economic outcomes, and social status of pastoral women in Africa. According to Patel’s (2014) study of entrepreneurship education and training programs, production training is supplementary likely to go ahead to enhanced trade exercise many females if it is of average to the maximum concentration that is contented is simplified for short capable entrepreneurs and the training focuses on realistic skills or applications. Technical assistance or follow-up training is helpful for women entrepreneurs, particularly if it is personalized.

Cho & Honorati (2014), that Personal area program positively impacts the effectiveness of entrepreneurship training programs.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

This study aims to realize effective training and its contribution to small entrepreneur development. Besides, the following specific objectives were addressed as well.

1. To examine the entrepreneurs who applied their training knowledge in creating small enterprises.
2. To measure the effectiveness of training on entrepreneurship development
3. To provide strategic policy measures for the effective exercises of training knowledge in creating several entrepreneurs.

1.3. Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurship in Bangladesh has achieved unparalleled growth in terms of dimensions and diversity of business since its early days. Bangladesh is a small country with a large population and insufficient industrial base.

The small industries are also considered as the small, medium, and micro enterprises (SMME) in the state. It is observed that most of the SMMEs supported businesses surveyed do not provide training according to the needs of their target market (GEM, 2002). There is no clear contradiction between the different prospects of entrepreneurship training and the different aspects of business skills training (Nieman, 2002).

Entrepreneurial training is confused with skill development training. The allegation of this finding is an early warning of the potential wastage of essential resources in Bangladesh. This situation calls for evaluation and consideration of the SME support program as a contribution to SMMEs.

Training is a process of teaching, educating, or informing people so that they may become as capable as possible of doing their tasks and become qualified to execute in positions of greater difficulty and responsibility. Training helps surmount the gap between actual performance and desired performance. Effective training is business or job-related and need-based.

In Bangladesh, most of the entrepreneurs are usually not addressing the actual training needs of SBs. Entrepreneur training is concerned with providing the entrepreneur or business person with knowledge, skills, and competencies to improve the efficiency of the individual (Nieman, 2000).

1.4. Hypothesis of the Study

In the study, several hypotheses were made for the development of entrepreneurship. The major hypotheses of the study are listed below, where whether the training is effective or not for the development of entrepreneurship was justified. H_0 : There has a positive impact on training on starting a business.

H_0 : There has a positive impact on training on starting a business.

H_0 : Training increases management skills.

H_0 : Training increases the power of solving problems or making decisions.

H_0 : Training increases the ability to use modern technology.

H_0 : Training increases financial analysis skills.

H_0 : Training provides adequate opportunities for practical exercises to apply in real-life situations.

H_0 : Training increases technical skills.

1.5. Rationality of the Study

Entrepreneurship is broadly recognized as a critical factor in economic improvement, employment generation, and industrial development of a country. Entrepreneurs are catalyzed by mobilizing capital, adding value to natural resources, and producing necessary goods and services that contribute to the growth of the national economy.

Proper training and education in entrepreneur's programs contribute to increasing the knowledge and confidence of potential entrepreneurs. This is contributing to expanding different categories of commercial and industrial entrepreneurship across the country. The organization development of agro-based and SEs is very significant in this respect.

Bangladesh is a small but developing country. So many people live in different areas of the country. To ensure a greater extent in the economy, we need a greater number of skilled, competent, and innovative entrepreneurs. The development of a country is possible if she creates a greater number of entrepreneurs. The entrepreneurs are the insistent catalyst for change in the global business. Entrepreneurship development is important not only to resolve the problem of unemployment but also to reach economic development of the country.

Entrepreneurship training and development programs are essential in every country, particularly in those countries where privately owned businesses have not been expanded. In the open market economy, a greater number of people in the countries become devoted to initiating and managing a personal-owned business, but they don't have proper knowledge of how to start and manage it. Moreover, developments of entrepreneurial skills of the people in a country are now considered as a competitive advantage of a country over others. To fulfill this vital need, nations have arranged a diversity of innovative and creative programs.

It is widely accepted that training increases entrepreneur skills but surprisingly, no worthwhile study has been conducted in this area so far. There are a few studies, in the form of articles and bulletins, were done to examine how far the knowledge and skills of entrepreneurs are transferred in reality. Without converting the learning of entrepreneurs into real business, no fruitful outcomes of training would occur. So, the researcher has selected the study to make an intensive study to measure the effect of entrepreneurial training programs on creating a greater number of industries, businesses, and commercial enterprises.

1.6. Limitations of the Study

No research is free from limitations. Like other studies, the present studies also suffer from several limitations that are as follows:

- The present study does not cover all the districts of Bangladesh because of the researcher's financial constraints, time constraints, and information constraints.
- As the questionnaire is arranged with the Likert Scale, there is always the chance of a halo effect or central tendency.
- The data for the study have been collected only from the entrepreneurs who have attended at least one entrepreneurship training program. The persons who have not attended any entrepreneurship training program are not covered for the study.
- Some beneficiary entrepreneurs may not have given truthful information.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter covers different issues related to the different aspects of entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship development, and problems faced by entrepreneurship training and education for entrepreneurship development, support services provided for entrepreneurship development from the previous publications as well as other issues that contribute to flourishing across the country.

Entrepreneurship is among the most valuable components for the long-run economic growth rate among countries. One view of entrepreneurship and revolution is that they are almost synonymous. Shane and Venkataraman (2000) state that the branch of entrepreneurship is defined by the analysis of "how, by whom and with what repercussion and opportunities to manufacture upcoming goods and services are discovered, estimated and utilized." This should recommend that innovation and entrepreneurship are nearly duplicates.

Chrisman & Sharma's (2005) study indicates demographic variations such as parents, educational qualifications, personal attitudes toward entrepreneurship, the environment of the university, and most educational backgrounds can help the development of entrepreneurial features in individuals. Entrepreneurship programs are one of the centers that can develop creativity processes in capable citizens. Merging the sciences of these courses with recognition of the wants of the market can be a strong step in producing successful organizations in today's development world.

Entrepreneurship is a dynamic task. An entrepreneur's success depends on changes in the environment. This study also checks the fundamental connection between entrepreneurship training upon entrepreneurial introduction in small enterprises. This small entrepreneur gives concentration to the entrepreneurial policy expansion in presented businesses, dissimilar to the earlier literature which focuses on the association between entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial dealing purpose to create innovative businesses. Ides opportunities for business. Entrepreneurs always need to make dissimilar dynamic decisions.

As Sikder Z H (1998) indicated small entrepreneurship expansion is a potential instrument to generate employment, promote balanced growth, more equitable distribution of income as well as diversification of the industrial structure in a country. Small industries may be started with less investment in simple technology, and have enormous potential for further growth and development in Bangladesh. Several steps have been taken by various institutions for the encouragement and improvement of small entrepreneurship. However, the estimated improvement in small entrepreneurship was not achieved. However, notably educated youths have come forward to promote this sector. This may be the result of training and other facilities offered by the government and different institutions.

As Leger, M., Arsenijevic, J., & Bosma, N. (2024) said a mass of training programmed contributions have occurred to mitigate the encounters of opening and nourishing a business in this context. Non-formal training (educational activities outside formal places of learning such as universities or schools) can support entrepreneurs develop important business skills.

Giné & Mansuri (2014) argued that entrepreneurship training improved business awareness for maximum sample CEO *representatives*. Entrepreneurship training contributes to increased enterprise exercise such as the footage of sales and the taking apart of business and family finances. It was also little developments in enterprise transactions particularly who won the raffle.

Debanjan Nag N. Das (2015) revealed that the improvement of small enterprises as an effective tool for employment generation and generating sustainable livelihood proper training methods for small entrepreneurial expertise improvement should be improved which will increase the efficiency of the small entrepreneurs

Glaub & Frese (2011) stated that entrepreneurship training programs have had constructive special effects on the emotional element, enterprise management skills, and element success. In addition, training on emotional elements has a positive contact on organization expansion.

Bauer (2011) states that female entrepreneurs benefit from career training that covers survival skills or another intellectual facet that helps them develop their self-dependence or intellect of empowerment. For example, woman entrepreneurs in Vermont claimed that commercial training improves their self-reliance as a result better ready for credit appliance processes. Rauth Bhardwaj (2014), an inspection of woman enterprise proprietors in India originates that training and education improve the self-assurance of female entrepreneurs. More particularly, training develops the skills needed to conduct research on their business and get information on consumers and competitors, while education helps them to find sources of funding.

Likewise, Patel (2014) found that career training programs have a small effect on business outcomes for women entrepreneurs. Cho & Honorati, (2014) added that women get the maximum gain from investment rather than education and training because they are extra credit-guarded than men. Patel (2014) claimed that training programs along with financial support had a bigger effect among females, commonly because they addressed

the economic limitations experienced by females. Moreover, training programs that are supported by funding facilities for an extensive period have a powerful impact and facilitate females to execute better transition utilization. Patel (2014) learned from training that programs that merge training and economics tend to be supplementary and costly to individual training programs. Furthermore, yet though the advantage of the joint initiatives is larger than the training program only the former may not be extra price efficient.

According to Patel's (2014) study of entrepreneurship education and training programs, production training is supplementary likely to go ahead to enhanced trade exercise among females if it is of average to the maximum concentration that is contented is simplified for short capable entrepreneurs and the training focuses on realistic skills or applications. Technical assistance or follow-up training is helpful for women entrepreneurs, particularly if it is personalized.

Cho & Honorati (2014) that personal area program has a positive impact on the effectiveness of entrepreneurship training programs.

For the growth of entrepreneurship or small business, Mac Rae (1991) discovered that the training, education, and experience of the higher executive are the main variations connecting high-expansion and low-expansion SME businesses. Nager Merwe (1999), Jennings and Beaver (1995), etc. highlight that small business crash is commonly an effect of low managerial capability. There are also training-linked issues in this area, the main trouble being prescribed training, as a small firm is less likely to give training to all levels of employees than a large firm (Jones and Pettigrew, 1991; Johnson, 1999). There is much research on the problems, challenges, and constraints of entrepreneurship expansion in Bangladesh. Among them, Bhattacharya and Hossain (2006) and Ahmed (2006) and Ahmed (2002) indicated complex documentation in the consumer's section, a shortage of automatic consumers policy etc. as the main troubles bar the expansion of any trade in Bangladesh that ever may be the size of business.

It is observed that there has been a quick explosion of entrepreneurship education. Brockhaus (2001) found that "one of the initial courses (in small business or entrepreneurship) was provided at the Harvard Business School in 1947. Peter Drucker advised additional subjects at New York University in 1953". Nevertheless, it was only in the most recent two decades of the 20th century that every great concentration was rewarded by the academic world for the development of entrepreneurship through educational programs (Hill, 1986; Scoot and Twomey, 1988).

Chowdhury (1996) conducted a study on "Entrepreneurship Training in Bangladesh". In his study, he analyzed that in Bangladesh different training institutions conducted entrepreneurial development training programs. He indicates that entrepreneurial training in Bangladesh is at the infant stage and is unable to meet the needs of the country. Again, he points out that effective entrepreneurship training warrants systematic assessment of the training needs of the entrepreneurs, devising proper training methodology, facilitating useful learning processes, and proper evaluation of the training results.

Martin et al., (2013), entrepreneurship education and training is successful in improving connotations and encouragement outcomes ensuring more start-ups. He also added that our academic sympathetic of how and why entrepreneurship training utilizes an activist pressure on entrepreneurial ability is at rest missing. Gielnik et al., (2015), particularly, our understanding concerning, inventing and upgrading training to raise entrepreneurship successfully is somewhat amazingly inadequate. Martinez et al., (2010), the Global Entrepreneurship record particular statement on entrepreneurship training, "We require additional studies on entrepreneurship training mostly on whether and in what explicit ways training create a variant".

According to Kimwolo, Saina, and Cheserek (2012), entrepreneurial training and development are the referred to a process that could delegate persons to obtain the required ability to keep and increase the self-confidence to search for durable market ideas and business opportunities for their goods or services. Both of them are these sets of attitudes, behaviors, awareness, and knowledge that provide individual utility and are extremely final to the continued existence and development of small businesses (Hellriegel, Slocum, Stuede, Klopper, Louw, & Oosthuizen, 2008). Izquierdo and Muelins (2008) identified that apprentice self-confidence in fruitfully executing specific duties as finding current business advantages, constructing fresh products, thinking innovatively, and commercializing an idea or innovative improvement. Following these definitions, the make is surrounded in this study as the required training program, open by the Center for African Entrepreneurship Research, Bayero University Kano, to all fresher students of the organization, which attention on the improvement and encouragement of entrepreneurial performance among the students.

Sylvia Gavigan, Klavs Ciprikis & Thomas Cooney (2020), in their study that entrepreneurship training may build up employment marketplace outcomes of personals; small is identified the effect of entrepreneurship training on self-enrollment in Uganda. In this research, a sample of 300 outback females in Uganda is taken on before and four months after taking part in an entrepreneurship training program to observe the effect of entrepreneurship training on self-enrollment. Business skills and business ability indices are utilized as considerations of training success, and a self-enrollment probity regression model is used to examine the effect of training on self-enrollment. The key results of this revision recommend that a rise in the business knowledge index and the business capability index by one unit can lead to a 6 percent and 2.7 percent rise in the possibility of individual self-enrollment. These results are vital for the plan and accomplishment of suitable strategy and policy to develop the work marketplace outcomes of females in rustic Uganda.

According to Sylvia Gavigan, Thomas M. Cooney, and Klavs Ciprikis (2023), an entrepreneurship training expansion of 25% entrepreneurial knowledge and again education training opportunities can expand the community status of countryside women functioning in agriculture. Again, this research can update managers, economists, and governments on the settlement of suitable education and training programs to progress the family values, economic outcomes, and social status of pastoral women in Africa.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Population

The study populations comprise the potential entrepreneurs of small businesses in Bangladesh. Specifically, the entrepreneurs who took their training from different organizations such as government institutions, NGOs, SMEs, SCITI, or others are the target population in our study. The information collected through several sources like training organizations, Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC), Jute Diversification Promotion Centre (JDPC), Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA), etc. give that most training centers as well as entrepreneurs are available in Dhaka and Chittagong divisions.

3.2 Sample

The sample of the survey is the ideal part of the population which consists of existing and potential entrepreneurs who have already taken training from various institutions on the development of small businesses representing various sectors of industries. A sample of 401 entrepreneurs has been taken from the population for the study. The respondents have been provided with structured questionnaires.

3.3 Sampling Design

In this study, convenience sampling was used to select the individuals for interview. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique in which subjects have been specified for interview for the reason of their suitable ease of use and closeness to the investigator.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

In a study of sample size determination, Cochran (1977) proposed a formula. The goal of the computation is to decide on a sufficient sample size that can provide good estimates for the entire population with excellent accuracy. The presumption of being tired is connected to several variables of the population such as the proportion, mean, standard deviation, etc.

3.5 Strategies for Determining Sample Size

In this study, Simple random sampling (SRS) and convenient sampling have been used to determine sample size and I have considered a 95% confidence level with a margin of error of 0.05.

3.6 Collection of Data

The data used in this study have been collected from primary sources. In this research, the questionnaires were either directly given to respondents or responses based on questionnaires from the respondents. The face-to-face interview technique has been used to make the questions understandable to the respondents who have been educated in irrelevant fields, are less educated, or are not amicable with many of the things included in the questionnaire. The questionnaire method has been used to design the basic questions related to all aspects of the impact of training and training effectiveness. Making

the questionnaire is a critical task, which has been touched with adequate attention to the content of the training in small businesses. Both open-ended and closed questions have been included in the questionnaire. The study required secondary data have been collected through a widespread literature review, articles published in national and international journals, electronic journals, relevant websites, various government, and non-government publications, different test books on entrepreneurship, various research books on entrepreneurship, statistical reports, research reports, newspapers, magazines etc.

3.7 Designing the Questionnaire

The questionnaire has been divided into 2(two) sections to incorporate all aspects of the search. The first section (1) included background of characteristics. The second contained the effectiveness of training and consisted of questions shown in the table below:

Table 1: Several sections of questionnaires

Name of the Section	Contents of the Section	Number of Questions
Section-1	Background of Characteristics	33
Section-2	Effectiveness of Training	13

3.8 Statistical Tools

As the objective of the study is to find out effective training and its contribution towards small entrepreneur development., frequency distribution comes as the first analysis tool, and paired t-test, chi-square test, proportion test, multiple linear regression analysis, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and ordinal logistic regression analysis have been used to find out the results for study purpose. The data will be inserted into SPSS 20 and the analysis was done by using STATA 14.

3.9 Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test is a calculation of how matched our data for combining. The test measures sampling sufficiency for every variable in the model and for the entire model. The statistic is a calculation of the proportion of variance among variables that might be common variance.

3.10 Cronbach's Alpha (α) Test

Cronbach's alpha is a measure of inside reliability, that is, how intimately connected a set of items are as a group. It is considered to be a calculation of scale reliability. It can be printed as a function of the number of test items and the average inter-correlation among the items.

3.11 Ethical Statement

This study employed a primary dataset, and participants were not provided any financial incentives to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the collected data. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the survey at any time without the need for justification. Before data collection, the entire questionnaire was read to the participants,

and their verbal consent was obtained. Furthermore, participants provided consent for the publication of the analyzed survey results while ensuring the exclusion of their identifiable information. The survey was conducted face-to-face, adhering fully to the principles outlined in the Helsinki Declaration on human participant research.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3.1 describes the background characteristics of entrepreneurs. In this research, 401 entrepreneurs were selected to serve the purpose of the study. Among the participants, more than two-thirds were male (72.57%).

The highest participation was found in the study from the middle-aged entrepreneurs (30-40 years) and the lowest participation was found from the young entrepreneurs (below 30 years).

Most of the participants were from the Dhaka division (71.25%), and the participants from other divisions like Chattogram and others were the lowest and almost equal (~14%).

Again, more than 50% of entrepreneurs had business in urban areas (66.08%), whereas about 34% of entrepreneurs had business in rural.

The involvement of married entrepreneurs (86.03%) in entrepreneurship was six times more compared to unmarried entrepreneurs (13.97%).

More than three-fourths of entrepreneurs (75.31%) did not have business before training, but their counterparts (24.69%) had business before training.

The participation was highest for the entrepreneurs who had taken from government institutions (34.66%) compared to other training organizations, and the lowest participation was counted for the entrepreneurs who had taken from non-government organizations (NGO) (10.97%).

Table 3.1: Background characteristics of entrepreneurs

Background Characteristics	N =401	Percentage
Gender		
Female	110	27.73
Male	291	72.57
Age of Entrepreneur		
Age<30	76	18.95
Age 30-40	171	42.64
Age>40	154	38.40
Area of Training Center		
Dhaka	285	71.25
Chattogram	58	14.50
Others	57	14.25
Area of Business Location		
Rural	136	33.92
Urban	265	66.08
Level of Education		
Pre-secondary	37	9.23

Background Characteristics	N =401	Percentage
Secondary and Higher	364	90.77
Marital Status		
Married	345	86.03
Un-married	56	13.97
Nature of Training		
Agro Product	80	19.95
Cloth	58	14.46
Workshop	51	12.72
Jute & Handicraft	83	20.70
Others	129	32.17
Business before Training		
Yes	99	24.69
No	302	75.31
Type of Training Organization		
Govt. Institution	139	34.66
NGO	44	10.97
SME	52	12.97
SCITI	76	18.95
Others	90	22.44
Duration of Training		
Below 3 Months	121	30.17
3-6 Months	207	51.62
6+ Months	73	18.20
Content of Training		
Skill Based	91	22.69
Technical	52	12.97
New Business Creation and Skill Based	220	54.89
Others	38	9.48
Number of Employees		
Below 5	186	46.38
5-10	124	30.92
10+	91	22.69
Initial Investment in Business		
Below 30000	190	47.38
30000-50000	110	27.43
50000+	101	25.19

In Table 3.2, the null hypothesis was defined as “the proportion of two categories or groups (Yes and No) of the indicators are equal (*i.e.* $H_0: \pi_1 = \pi_2$)” and the alternative hypothesis was defined as “the proportion of yes group is greater than the proportion of no group (*i.e.* $H_1: \pi_1 > \pi_2$)”. If the null hypothesis is rejected, the test is significant and hence we can conclude that the proportion of the yes group is greater than the proportion of the no group *i.e.*, the training has a significant effect on the development of small entrepreneurship.

The proportion test gave significant results ($p < 0.01$) for all the indicators of the effectiveness of training.

For the first indicator, the null hypothesis is that there is no need for Training for starting a business which is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis: that there is a positive impact of training on starting a business is accepted. Among the entrepreneurs, 97% entrepreneurs said that the training was essential for starting a business, and there was a significant difference between the yes and no groups of entrepreneurs ($p < 0.001$).

For the second indicator, the null hypothesis: that training does not increase management skills is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis: that training increases management skills is accepted. About 84% of entrepreneurs believed that training increased their management skills, and the proportion test revealed that entrepreneurs of the yes group were significantly higher than the entrepreneurs of the no group. Similar results were also found for the remaining indicators for measuring the effectiveness of training.

For the third indicator, the null hypothesis: that training does not increase the power of solving problems or taking decisions is rejected and the alternative hypothesis: that training increases the power of solving problems or making decisions is accepted. More than three-fourths of entrepreneurs claimed that the training increased their power to solve problems or to take decisions related to business and there was a significant difference between yes and no groups of entrepreneurs ($p < 0.001$).

For the fourth indicator, the null hypothesis: that training does not increase the ability to use modern technology is rejected and the alternative hypothesis: that training increases abilities to use modern technology is accepted since the p-value is less than 0.05. About 75% of entrepreneurs justified that the training has increased their ability to use modern technology in their business.

For the seventh indicator, the null hypothesis: training does not provide adequate opportunities for practical exercises to apply in real-life situations is rejected and the alternative hypothesis training provides adequate opportunities for practical exercises to apply in real-life situations is accepted since the p-value is less than 0.05. Since all the indicators showed significant results, it could be said that the training has a positive effect on entrepreneurship and to development of small businesses.

Table 3.2: Proportion test on several indicators to measure the effectiveness of training on small entrepreneurship

Variables	Categories	Percentage	p-value	95% CI of proportion
Training was essential for starting business	Yes	97.01	<0.001***	0.95-0.99
	No	02.99		
Training has increased management skills	Yes	84.04	<0.001***	0.81-0.88
	No	15.96		
Training has increased the power to solve problems or to take decision	Yes	78.05	<0.001***	0.74-0.82
	No	21.95		
Training has increased the ability to use modern technology	Yes	75.56	<0.001***	0.71-0.80
	No	24.44		
Training has increased the promotional process	Yes	62.59	<0.001***	0.58-0.67
	No	37.41		
	Yes	61.35	<0.001***	0.57-0.66

Training has increased the ability to handle the client	No	38.65		
Training has provided adequate opportunities for practical exercises to apply in real-life situations	Yes	92.77	<0.001***	0.90-0.95
	No	07.23		
Training has increased financial analysis skills	Yes	63.59	<0.001***	0.59-0.68
	No	36.41		
Training has increased the power to handle risk	Yes	58.35	<0.001***	0.54-0.63
	No	41.65		
Training has increased marketing skill	Yes	56.61	0.004***	0.52-0.62
	No	43.39		
Training has increased my analytical skill	Yes	65.59	<0.001***	0.61-0.70
	No	34.41		
Training has increased technical skill	Yes	78.05	<0.001***	0.74-0.82
	No	21.95		
Training has increased feasibility skill	Yes	77.05	<0.001***	0.75-0.83
	No	22.95		

*p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Table 3.3 shows the prevalence and association of the effectiveness of training with several background characteristics, where the associations were justified by using the chi-square test. In this analysis, the null hypothesis was defined as “there was no association of independent variable with the dependent variable effectiveness of training” and the alternative hypothesis was defined as “there was an association of independent variable with the dependent variable effectiveness of training”. If the null hypothesis is rejected then we can accept the alternative hypothesis and the test will be significant, and hence we may conclude that there was a significant association of the independent variable with the dependent variable effectiveness of training.

In the case of training centers, area of the business location, level of education, marital status, nature of training, business before training, type of training organization, duration of the training, the content of training, training opportunities, and the initial investment on business the null hypothesis of “there was no association of the variables with the effectiveness of training” is rejected i.e. the above variables have a significant association with the effectiveness of training. The training centers of the Dhaka division have a higher effectiveness of training compared to Chattogram or other divisions.

A significant association between the area of business location and the effectiveness of training was also found ($p < 0.01$), where the effectiveness of training was higher for urban groups of entrepreneurs compared to rural entrepreneurs. The level of education was the important factor that showed a significant association with the effectiveness of training ($p < 0.01$), where secondary or higher-educated entrepreneurs had higher training effectiveness compared to pre-secondary-educated entrepreneurs.

Duration of training was also a significant factor, where 3-6 months of training was enough for training effectiveness to develop small enterprises. The technical-based training gave entrepreneurs higher effectiveness compared to skill-based training or others.

Table 3.3: Association of effectiveness of training with several background characteristics based on chi-square test

Background Characteristics	Effectiveness of Training			p-value
	Low	Medium	High	
Gender				
Male	30.93	35.74	33.33	0.185
Female	40.00	28.18	31.82	
Age of Entrepreneur				
Age<30	38.16	47.37	14.47	0.001***
Age 30-40	36.26	29.82	33.92	
Age>40	27.92	31.17	40.91	
Area of Training Center				
Dhaka	27.37	31.23	41.40	<0.001***
Chattagram	50.00	41.38	08.62	
Others	47.37	36.84	15.79	
Area of Business Location				
Urban	27.92	29.06	43.02	<0.001***
Rural	44.12	42.65	13.24	
Level of Education				
Pre-secondary	48.65	45.95	05.41	0.001***
Secondary and Higher	31.87	32.42	35.71	
Marital Status				
Married	30.72	33.62	35.65	0.004***
Un-married	50.00	33.93	16.07	
Nature of Training				
Agro Product	35.00	45.00	20.00	0.001***
Cloth	50.00	27.59	22.41	
Workshop	27.45	41.18	31.37	
Jute & Handicraft	32.53	20.48	46.99	
Others	27.91	34.88	37.21	
Business before Training				
Yes	43.43	35.35	21.21	0.009***
No	30.13	33.11	36.75	
Type of Training Organization				
Govt. Institution	38.13	36.69	25.18	<0.001***
NGO	25.00	27.27	47.73	
SME	38.46	42.31	19.23	
SCITI	19.74	19.74	60.53	
Others	38.89	38.89	22.22	
Duration of Training				
Below 3 Months	44.63	33.06	22.31	0.002***
3-6 Months	26.09	32.85	41.06	
6+ Months	35.62	36.99	27.40	
Content of Training				
Skill Based	45.05	30.77	24.18	0.026**
Technical	23.08	40.38	36.54	
New Business Creation and Skill Based	31.82	35.45	32.73	
Others	28.95	21.05	50.00	
Training Opportunities				
Inadequate	40.88	35.22	23.90	<0.001***

Background Characteristics	Effectiveness of Training			p-value
	Low	Medium	High	
Moderate	42.86	42.86	14.29	
Adequate	08.82	18.63	72.55	
Initial Investment on Business				
Below 30000	41.58	34.74	23.68	0.002***
30000-50000	24.55	34.55	40.91	
50000+	27.72	30.69	41.58	

*p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Table 3.4 displayed the odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence intervals and p-values of the effectiveness of training for several background characteristics of entrepreneurs obtained from ordinal logistic regression analysis. In the analysis, the ordinal logistic regression model has been applied to find out the potential factors that might be directly related to the effectiveness of training. From Table 3.4 some potential factors were identified that significantly influenced the training effectiveness. The potential factors are gender, area of the training center, level of education, business before training, type of training organization, duration of the training, training opportunities, and initial business investment. That means, in these factors the null hypothesis “there was no effect of the certain independent variable on the dependent variable income” is rejected and the alternative hypothesis “there was an effect of the certain independent variable on the dependent variable income” is accepted. The other factors selected in the study did not show a significant association with the effectiveness of training that means in these factors the null hypothesis “there was no effect of a certain independent variable on the dependent variable income is accepted.

The training effectiveness differed significantly between business in rural and business in urban areas and it was 2.31 times more for the urban group of entrepreneurs than the group of rural entrepreneurs (OR 2.31, CI: 1.29-4.14; p-value = 0.005). For the entrepreneurs who had no business before training, the training was effective and it was 2.31 times higher compared to the entrepreneurs who had business before training (OR = 2.31, CI: 1.36-3.91, p-value = 0.002). The effectiveness of training was 2.12 times higher for entrepreneurs who invested initially in TK. 30,000-50,000 in business compared to entrepreneurs who invested initially below TK. 30,000 in business (OR = 2.12, CI: 1.22-3.67, p-value = 0.007).

Table 3.4: The odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence intervals and p-values of the effectiveness of training for several background characteristics of entrepreneurs obtained from ordinal logistic regression analysis

Background Characteristics	OR	95% CI	p-value
Gender			
Female	1.00		
Male	2.79	1.52–5.12	0.001***
Age of Entrepreneur			
Age<30	1.00		
Age 30-40	0.82	0.43–1.57	0.556
Age>40	0.73	0.35–1.53	0.407

Background Characteristics	OR	95% CI	p-value
Area of Training Center			
Dhaka	1.00		
Chattogram	0.23	0.10–0.54	0.001***
Others	0.47	0.22–1.02	0.056*
Area of Business Location			
Rural	1.00		
Urban	2.31	1.29–4.14	0.005***
Level of Education			
Pre-secondary	1.00		
Secondary and Higher	2.73	1.20–6.19	0.016**
Marital Status			
Married	1.53	0.74–3.17	0.247
Un-married	1.00		
Nature of Training			
Agro Product	1.00		
Cloth	0.47	0.19–1.17	0.105
Workshop	0.55	0.14–2.10	0.378
Jute & Handicraft	0.86	0.37–2.02	0.731
Others	0.80	0.38–1.68	0.551
Business before Training			
Yes	1.00		
No	2.31	1.36–3.91	0.002***
Type of Training Organization			
Govt. Institution	1.00		
NGO	2.28	0.82–4.32	0.061*
SME	1.08	0.48–2.13	0.851
SCITI	3.01	1.27–6.06	0.007***
Others	1.10	0.45–2.24	0.824
Duration of Training			
Below 3 Months	1.00		
3-6 Months	1.73	0.97–3.10	0.065*
6+ Months	1.06	0.47–2.42	0.883
Content of Training			
Skill Based	1.00		
Technical	2.10	0.63–7.01	0.230
New Business Creation and Skill Based	1.59	0.76–3.31	0.216
Others	0.96	0.36–2.55	0.937
Training Opportunities			
Inadequate	1.00		
Moderate	1.45	0.92–2.58	0.102
Adequate	16.39	8.22–32.68	<0.001***
Completion of Field Work on Training			
Yes	2.46	1.48–4.10	0.001***
No	1.00		
Initial Investment on Business			
Below 30000	1.00		
30000-50000	2.12	1.22–3.67	0.007***
50000+	1.62	0.91–2.90	0.102

*p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) The training organizations should improve the quality of exam for entering the training program because the competitive exam cannot give the trainees higher effectiveness of training to develop the business.
- 2) The adequate training opportunities give the trainees higher effectiveness of training. Thus, all training organizations should ensure adequate training opportunities for the development of female entrepreneurship.
- 3) The government training organization gives the trainee slower effectiveness of training. Thus, the quality of this organization should improve for the development of entrepreneurship. The government should monitor regularly the government training organizations.
- 4) The training program should have fieldwork with usual training because the entrepreneurs who completed the fieldwork in training have higher training effectiveness. Thus, the training organizations should also take fieldwork training among the trainees.

6. CONCLUSION

An entrepreneur plays a fundamental role in innovation, creation, employment, wealth, and economic growth in manufacturing and developing countries. Entrepreneurship need not be born but may also be improved through education and training. That is the basic philosophy behind entrepreneurial programs.

The educational and training organizations, such as Universities, SCITI, SME Foundation, BITAC, business management institutions, NGOs, technical institutions, and other govt. and non govt. organizations increased in entrepreneurship can donate considerably to the expansion of entrepreneurs and thus to the trade and industry expansion of the country.

The focus of entrepreneurship programs has to divert from simply training the person to improving the person. It is essential to train them properly to improve their skill and capabilities in innovations and the creation of ideas for business.

Training is also important for motivating people to invest in new and old businesses and to remove the fear of business to start to improve their quality and to make them conscious of the obstacles in conducting business. These trainings help entrepreneurs to make their business easier more profitable and more effective.

Training helps to remove different business problems and it shows the way to go ahead to success in business. Training brings new technologies, makes participants knowledgeable, and motivates them about innovations. So, training has a strong impact on entrepreneurial decisions and an entrepreneur should attend training to ensure success in entrepreneurship and to secure investment also.

Availability of data and materials: The datasets in the study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Competing interest: The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Funding: Funding sources are not available in this research.

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